

Operators induced by fuzzy stack on a fuzzy topological space

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Abstract –

In the present paper we introduce operators ϕ_s, ψ_s induced by given fuzzy stack S and fuzzy topology τ . With the help of operators and the collection τ^s , a new fuzzy topology τ^{s*} is obtained. It is shown that $\tau \subseteq \tau^s \subseteq \tau^{s*}$. We have also shown various relations between the fuzzy stack oriented collections and given fuzzy topology. A suitability condition is applied on fuzzy stack, which makes the fuzzy topology better defined.

Key words - Fuzzy grill, ϕ_s - operator, ψ_s - operator

1. INTRODUCTION

Choquet [2] introduced the notion of grills in general topology. In fuzzy setting, the notion of fuzzy grill and fuzzy stack was introduced by K.K. Azad [1]. Since then fuzzy grills and fuzzy stacks are studied by many authors in topological proximity and nearness spaces [4, 5, 8, 10, 12].

In 2007, Roy and Mukherjee [5] introduced an operator defined by a grill on a topological space. Das & Mukherjee [4] introduced an operator by fuzzy grill on fuzzy topological space and showed that it satisfy Kuratowski closure axioms.

In 2012, Min and Kim [11] studied operators induced by stacks on a topological space. In the present paper, we introduced operators with the help of fuzzy stack on a given fuzzy topology. It is obviously a generalized notion of operator defined by fuzzy grill on a fuzzy topological space in [4]. In section 3, the operator ϕ_s is defined with the help of a fuzzy stack S and fuzzy topology τ and some of the basic properties are studied. Further the operator ψ_s is defined by operator ϕ_s . The collection τ^s of fuzzy sets induced by operator ϕ_s are studied. In particular, we show that collection of fuzzy sets τ^s induced by ψ_s is a super collection of given fuzzy topology τ . In section 4, we applied some suitability condition on fuzzy stack. If S is a fuzzy stack on I^X and τ is a fuzzy topology on I^X then, for $V \in \tau, B \notin S \Rightarrow V - B \in \tau^s$, it is shown with the help of suitability condition that $\tau^s = \{V - B : V \in \tau, B \notin S\}$ where $V, B \in I^X$.

2. PRELIMINARIES

A fuzzy set A in a set X is a function on X into the closed unit interval $[0, 1]$ of the real line. Support of $A = \{x \in X : A(x) > 0\}$ is denoted by $\text{Supp } A$. The fuzzy sets in X taking on the constant values 0 and 1 are denoted by 0_X and 1_X respectively. For $A, B \in I^X, A \leq B$ if $A(x) \leq B(x)$ for each $x \in X$. By AqB , we mean that A is quasi - coincident with

B . i.e. AqB implies $A(x) + B(x) > 1$ for some $x \in X$. The negations of these statements are denoted by $A\bar{q}B$. A fuzzy singleton or a fuzzy point with support X and value p ($0 < p \leq 1$) is denoted by x_p . The collection of all open q -nbds of any fuzzy point x_p is denoted by $Q(x_p)$. A subfamily β of the fuzzy topology τ of an fts (X, τ) is a base for τ iff for each fuzzy singleton x_p in (X, τ) and for each open q -nbd U of $x_p, x_p qB$ for some $B \in \beta$ with $B \leq U$. A fuzzy point x_p is called an adherence point of fuzzy set A if every open q -nbd of x_p is a quasi - coincident with A and $Cl(A)$ is the union of all adherence points of A . $M(A)$ is set of molecules of I^X in A . $VM(\downarrow A) = A$, for $A \in I^X$ where $\downarrow A = \{b \in P : \exists a \in A \text{ s.t. } b \leq a\}$, P is a Poset.

3 COLLECTION τ^s INDUCED BY FUZZY STACK S

Definition 3.1 - Let (I^X, τ) be a fuzzy topological space and S be a fuzzy stack on I^X . For $A \in I^X$, a mapping $\phi_s : I^X \rightarrow I^X$ denoted by $\phi_s(A) = \bigvee \{x_p : A * U \in S \text{ for all } U \in Q(x_p)\}$ is called operator associated with fuzzy stack S and fuzzy topology on I^X .

Remarks 3.2 - For $A \in I^X, x_p \notin \phi_s(A)$ iff $\exists U \in Q(x_p)$ such that $U * A \notin S$.

Proposition 3.3 - Let (I^X, τ) be a fuzzy topological space and S be a fuzzy stack on I^X .

- (i) For $A, B \in I^X, A \leq B \Rightarrow \phi_s(A) \leq \phi_s(B)$.
- (ii) If S_1 and S_2 are two fuzzy stack on I^X with $S_1 \subseteq S_2$, then $\phi_{S_1}(A) \leq \phi_{S_2}(A)$ for $A \in I^X$.
- (iii) For any fuzzy stack S on I^X and $A \in I^X$, if $A \notin S$, then $\phi_s(A) = 0_X$.

Proof –

- (i) Let $x_p \leq \phi_s(A)$, then for all $U \in Q(x_p), A * U \in S$. Since $A \leq B \Rightarrow A * U \leq B * U$; but S is fuzzy stack so $B * U \in S$ for all $U \in Q(x_p)$, this implies $x_p \leq \phi_s(B)$.
- (ii) Suppose $x_p \leq \phi_{S_1}(A)$, this implies that for all $U \in Q(x_p), A * U \in S_1 \subseteq S_2$, then $x_p \leq \phi_{S_2}(A)$.
- (iii) Let $x_p \leq \phi_s(A) \& A \notin S \Rightarrow$ for all $U \in Q(x_p), A * U \in S$, so we arrive at a contradiction. Thus $\phi_s(A) = 0_X$ if $A \notin S$.

Remark 3.3.1 - $\phi_s(0_X) = 0_X$

Example 3.3.2 - $\emptyset_S(I_X) \neq I_X$

We will prove $\exists a x_p$ such that $x_p \notin \emptyset_S(I_X)$ but $x_p \leq I_X$. Let $X = \{a, b\}$, $\tau = \{c, 0_X, I_X\}$ where $c(a) = 0.2$, $c(b) = 0.3$. Let $S = \{1_X \text{ all fuzzy sets } T \text{ s.t. } 0.3 \leq T(a) \leq 1, 0.4 \leq T(b) \leq 1\}$, here, S is a fuzzy stack and τ is a fuzzy topology.

Proposition 3.4 - Let (I^X, τ) be a fuzzy topological space and S be a fuzzy stack on I^X . Then, for $A \in I^X$.

- (i) $\emptyset_S(A) \leq cl(A)$
- (ii) $cl(\emptyset_S(A)) \leq \emptyset_S(A)$

Proof -

- (i) Suppose that $x_p \notin cl(A)$, then there exist an open q -nbd U of x_p in X s.t. $U \bar{q} A$, that is, $A(y) + U(y) \leq 1$ for each $y \in X$ and hence $A * U = 0_X \notin S$, then $x_p \notin \emptyset_S(A)$.
- (ii) Let $x_p \leq cl(\emptyset_S(A))$ and $U \in Q(x_p)$, then $\emptyset_S(A) q U$ that is, there exist $y \in X$ such that $\emptyset_S(A)(y) + U(y) > 1$, let $\emptyset_S(A)(y) = t$, this implies $y_t \leq \emptyset_S(A)$ and $U \in Q(y_t) \Rightarrow A * U \in S \Rightarrow x_p \leq \emptyset_S(A)$.

Corollary 3.4.1 - For a fuzzy topological space (I^X, τ) , $\emptyset_S(\emptyset_S(A)) \leq \emptyset_S(A)$ where $A \in I^X$.

Proof - By 3.4 (i) $\emptyset_S(\emptyset_S(A)) \leq cl(\emptyset_S(A))$ and by 3.4 (ii) $cl(\emptyset_S(A)) \leq \emptyset_S(A)$, this implies $\emptyset_S(\emptyset_S(A)) \leq \emptyset_S(A)$.

Proposition 3.5 - For fuzzy topological space (I^X, τ) , \emptyset_S is closed for $A \in I^X$.

Proof - By 3.4 (ii), $cl(\emptyset_S(A)) \leq \emptyset_S(A)$ and by definition of closure, $\emptyset_S(A) \leq cl(\emptyset_S(A))$. Then $cl(\emptyset_S(A)) = \emptyset_S(A)$. This shows that $\emptyset_S(A)$ is closed for $A \in I^X$.

Definition 3.6 - Let S be a fuzzy stack on fuzzy topological space (I^X, τ) . We define $\psi_S : I^X \rightarrow I^X$ by $\psi_S(A) = A \vee \emptyset_S(A)$ where $A \in I^X$.

Proposition 3.7 - The above defined operator ψ_S satisfy the following conditions

- (i) $\psi_S(0_X) = 0_X$
- (ii) $A \leq \psi_S(A)$ for $A \in I^X$
- (iii) For $A, B \in I^X$, $A \leq B \Rightarrow \psi_S(A) \leq \psi_S(B)$
- (iv) For $A, B \in I^X$, $\psi_S(A \wedge B) \leq \psi_S(A) \wedge \psi_S(B)$

Proof - (i) & (ii) Follows from definition

- (iii) For $A, B \in I^X$, $\psi_S(A) = A \vee \emptyset_S(A) \leq B \vee \emptyset_S(B) = \psi_S(B)$, so $A \leq B$ implies $\psi_S(A) \leq \psi_S(B)$.
- (iv) For $A, B \in I^X$, $A \wedge B \leq A, B$. Using proposition 3.7, $\psi_S(A \wedge B) \leq \psi_S(A), \psi_S(B)$, which gives $\psi_S(A \wedge B) \leq \psi_S(A) \wedge \psi_S(B)$.

Example 3.7.1 - Let (I^X, τ) be a fuzzy topological space where $X = \{a, b\}$, $\tau = \{c, 0_X, I_X\}$, $c(a) = 0.5$, $c(b) = 0.2$. S be a fuzzy stack containing I_X and all fuzzy set S s.t. $S(a) > 0.1$, $S(b) > 0.2$, we will prove that $\psi_S(A \wedge B) \neq \psi_S(A) \wedge \psi_S(B)$, $A, B \in I^X$ s.t. Let $A(a) = 0.1$, $A(b) = 0.5$, $B(a) = 0.3$, $B(b) = 0.3$. Here $A \notin S$ so $\emptyset_S(A) = 0_X$, thus $\psi_S(A) = A \vee \emptyset_S(A) = A$. $(A \wedge B)(a) = 0.1$, $(A \wedge B)(b) = 0.3 \Rightarrow A \wedge B \notin S$ so $\emptyset_S(A \wedge B) = 0_X$, thus $\psi_S(A \wedge B) = (A \wedge B) \vee 0_X = A \wedge B$. $\psi_S(A) \wedge \psi_S(B) = A \wedge B$.

$B) = 0_X$, thus $\psi_S(A \wedge B) = (A \wedge B) \vee 0_X = A \wedge B$, $B(a) = 0.3$, $B(b) = 0.3$; $\emptyset_S(B) = a_{p_1} \vee b_{p_2}$ where $p_1 \leq 0.5$, $p_2 \leq 0.8$, $\psi_S(B)(a) = (B \vee \emptyset_S(B))(a) = 0.5$, $\psi_S(B)(b) = 0.8$, $\psi_S(A \wedge B) \neq \psi_S(A) \wedge \psi_S(B)$.

Example 3.7.2 - Let (I^X, τ) be a fuzzy topological space where $X = \{a, b\}$, $\tau = \{c, 0_X, I_X\}$, $c(a) = 0.5$, $c(b) = 0.2$. Let S be a fuzzy stack containing I_X and all fuzzy set S such that $S(a) > 0.1$, $S(b) > 0.2$. We will prove that $\psi_S(A \vee B) \neq \psi_S(A) \vee \psi_S(B)$, $A, B \in I^X$ such that Let $A(a) = 0.1$, $A(b) = 0.3$, $B(a) = 0.3$, $B(b) = 0.1$. $\psi_S(A) = A \vee \emptyset_S(A) = A \vee 0_X = A$, similarly $\psi_S(B) = B \vee \emptyset_S(B) = B \vee 0_X = B$. $(A \vee B)(a) = 0.3$, $(A \vee B)(b) = 0.3$, $\psi_S(A \vee B)(a) = 0.5$, $\psi_S(A \vee B)(b) = 0.8$, $\psi_S(A \vee B) \neq \psi_S(A) \vee \psi_S(B)$.

Definition 3.8 - Let (I^X, τ) be a fuzzy topological space and S be fuzzy stack on I^X , then $\tau^S = \{U \in I^X : \psi_S(I_X - U) = (I_X - U)\}$

Proposition 3.9.1 - Let (I^X, τ) be fuzzy topological space and S be a fuzzy stack on I^X . Then

- (i) $0_X, I_X \in \tau^S$
- (ii) If $U_p \in \tau^S$ for $p \in J$, then $\bigvee U_p \in \tau^S$

Proof -

- (i) Since $\psi_S(0_X) = 0_X$ and $\psi_S(I_X) = I_X \Rightarrow I_X, 0_X \in \tau^S$.
- (ii) Suppose $U_p \in \tau^S$ for all $\alpha \in J$. Let $U_p \in \tau^S$, then $\psi_S(I_X - U_p) = I_X - U_p$ and so $(I_X - U_p) \vee \emptyset_S(I_X - U_p) = (I_X - U_p)$. So $\emptyset_S(I_X - U_p) \leq I_X - U_p$. This shows $\emptyset_S(I_X - \bigvee U_p) \leq \emptyset_S(I_X - U_p) \leq I_X - U_p$, which gives $\emptyset_S(I_X - \bigvee U_p) \leq \bigwedge (I_X - U_p) = (I_X - \bigvee U_p)$. So $\psi_S(I_X - \bigvee U_p) = (I_X - \bigvee U_p)$. Hence $\bigvee U_p \in \tau^S$.

Remark 3.9.2 - Let (I^X, τ) be a fuzzy topological space and S be a fuzzy stack on I^X , elements of τ^S are said to be τ^S -open. If the complement of a fuzzy set is τ^S -open, then fuzzy set is called τ^S -closed.

Theorem 3.10 - Let (I^X, τ) be a fuzzy topological space and S be a fuzzy stack on I^X . Then for $V \in \tau$ and $A \notin S$, $V - A \in \tau^S$.

Proof - Suppose that $U = V - A$ s.t. $V \in \tau$ and $A \notin S$. We show that $\emptyset_S(I_X - U) \leq I_X - U$. Let there exists a fuzzy point x_p such that $x_p \leq \emptyset_S(I_X - U)$, but $x_p \notin I_X - U$, which implies that for each $W \in Q(x_p)$, $W + (I_X - U) - 1 \in S$. Since $W + I - U - 1 = W - U \in S$, $W - (V - A) \in S$, but $x_p \notin I_X - U \Rightarrow p > (I_X - U)(x) = 1 - (V - A)(x) \Rightarrow p + V(x) > 1 + A(x) \geq 1$ [In fact $V(x) \leq A(x)$ is not possible since in that case $(V - A)(x) = 0$, this implies $1 - (V - A)(x) = 1 - 0 < p$. Thus $V(x) > A(x)$ and $(V - A)(x) = V(x) - A(x)$. Then $p > 1 - (V - A)(x) = 1 - V(x) + A(x) \Rightarrow p + V(x) > 1 + A(x) \geq 1$.] Hence $V \in Q(x_p)$. As $V - (V - A) \in S$ but $V - (V - A) \leq A \Rightarrow A \in S$, contradiction to $A \notin S$. Then $\emptyset_S(I_X - U) \leq I_X - U$. Thus $V - A \in \tau^S$.

Corollary 3.10.1 - Let S be a fuzzy stack on (I^X, τ) , then $\tau \subseteq \tau^S$

Definition 3.11 -

For $A \in I^X$, we define $i_{\tau^S}: I^X \rightarrow I^X, c_{\tau^S}: I^X \rightarrow I^X$, such that $i_{\tau^S}(A) = \bigvee \{U \in I: U \leq A \text{ and } U \tau^S\}$, $c_{\tau^S}(A) = \bigwedge \{F \in I^X: A \leq F \text{ and } I_X - F \in \tau^S\}$.

Remark 3.11.1 - Let (I^X, τ) be a fuzzy topological space and S be a fuzzy stack on I^X . For $A \in I^X, x_p \leq i_{\tau^S}(A)$ if and only if there exists a τ^S -open set U such that $x_p \leq U$ and $U \leq A$.

Corollary 3.11.2 - Let (I^X, τ) be a fuzzy topological space and S be a fuzzy stack on I^X . If for $A \in I^X, x_p \leq i_{\tau^S}(A)$, then there exist $W \in Q(x_p)$ such that $(I_X - A) * W \notin S$.

Proof- Let $x_p \leq i_{\tau^S}(A)$ then there exists a τ^S -open set U such that $x_p \leq U$ and $U \leq A$. Then $I_X - A \leq I_X - U = \psi_S(I_X - U)$. But $x_p \notin \psi_S(I_X - U) \leq (I_X - U)$. So, there exists $W \in Q(x_p)$ such that $(I_X - U) * W \notin S \Rightarrow (I_X - A) * W \notin S$.

Theorem 3.12 - Let (I^X, τ) be a fuzzy topological space and S be a fuzzy stack on I^X . For $A, B \in I^X$

- (i) $i_{\tau^S}(0_X) = 0_X, i_{\tau^S}(I_X) = I_X$
- (ii) $i_{\tau^S}(A) \leq A$
- (iii) if $A \leq B$, then $i_{\tau^S}(A) \leq i_{\tau^S}(B)$
- (iv) $i_{\tau^S}(i_{\tau^S}(A)) = i_{\tau^S}(A)$
- (v) $i_{\tau^S}(A \wedge B) = i_{\tau^S}(A) \wedge i_{\tau^S}(B)$

Theorem 3.13 - Let (I^X, τ) be a fuzzy topological space and S be a fuzzy stack on I^X . For $A, B \in I^X$,

- (i) $c_{\tau^S}(I_X) = I_X, c_{\tau^S}(0_X) = 0_X$
- (ii) $A \leq c_{\tau^S}(A)$
- (iii) If $A \leq B \Rightarrow c_{\tau^S}(A) \leq c_{\tau^S}(B)$
- (iv) $c_{\tau^S}(c_{\tau^S}(A)) = c_{\tau^S}(A)$
- (v) $c_{\tau^S}(A \vee B) = c_{\tau^S}(A) \vee c_{\tau^S}(B)$

Remark 3.13.1 - c_{τ^S} is a Kuratowski closure operator

Theorem 3.14 - Let (I^X, τ) be a fuzzy topological space and S be a fuzzy stack on I^X . For $A, B \in I^X, A$ is τ^S -closed iff $\psi_S(A) = A$

Proof - For $A \in I^X, A$ is τ^S -closed iff $I_X - A$ is τ^S -open iff $\psi_S(I_X - (I_X - A)) = (I_X - (I_X - A))$ iff $\psi_S(A) = A$

Theorem 3.15 - Let (I^X, τ) be a fuzzy topological space and S be a fuzzy stack on I^X . For $A \in I^X$,

- (i) $A \notin S \Rightarrow I_X - A \in \tau^S$
- (ii) $\psi_S(A)$ is τ^S -closed
- (iii) $\psi_S(A) \leq c_{\tau^S}(A)$

Proof -

- (i) Let $A \notin S$, then $\psi_S(A) = 0_X, \psi_S(I_X - (I_X - A)) = \psi_S(A) = A \vee \psi_S(A) = A = I_X - (I_X - A)$, this implies $I_X - A \in \tau^S$.

- (ii) Since $\psi_S(\psi_S(A)) = \psi_S(A) \vee \psi_S(\psi_S(A)) = \psi_S(A)$, which gives $\psi_S(A)$ is τ^S -closed.
- (iii) Since $\psi_S(A) \leq \psi_S(c_{\tau^S}(A))$, we have $\psi_S(A) \leq \psi_S(c_{\tau^S}(A)) = c_{\tau^S}(A)$

Definition 3.16 - Define $\tau^{S*} = \{A \in I^X: c_{\tau^S}(I_X - A) = (I_X - A)\}$ also τ^{S*} is a fuzzy topology on I^X , where c_{τ^S} is a Kuratowski closure operator.

Note 3.16.1 - $\tau \subseteq \tau^{S*} \subseteq \tau^S$

Example 3.16.2 - In an fuzzy topological space (I^X, τ) , the trivial fuzzy stack is $I^X / \{0_X\}$. If we take $S = I^X / \{0_X\}$, this implies for $A \in I^X, \psi_S(A) = \psi_S(A) = cl(A) = c_{\tau^S}(A)$. In this case $\tau = \tau^{S*} = \tau^S$.

Proposition 3.17 - Let (I^X, τ) be a fuzzy topological space and S_1 and S_2 be fuzzy stack on I^X . For $A \in I^X$,

- (i) If $S_1 \subseteq S_2$, then $\tau^{S_2} \subseteq \tau^{S_1}$
- (ii) If $S_1 \subseteq S_2$, then $c_{\tau^{S_1}}(A) \leq c_{\tau^{S_2}}(A)$
- (iii) $\tau^{S_2*} \subseteq \tau^{S_1*}$, where $\tau^{S*} = \{A: c_{\tau^S}(I_X - A) = (I_X - A)\}$

Proof -

- (i) Since $\tau^S = \{A: \psi_S(I_X - A) = (I_X - A)\}$. Let $U \in \tau^{S_2}$, this implies $\psi_{S_2}(I_X - U) = (I_X - U) \Rightarrow \psi_{S_2}(I_X - U) \leq (I_X - U)$ but $S_1 \subseteq S_2$, so $\psi_{S_1}(I_X - U) \leq \psi_{S_2}(I_X - U) \leq (I_X - U) \Rightarrow \psi_{S_1}(I_X - U) = (I_X - U) \Rightarrow U \in \tau^{S_1}$
- (ii) Follows from definition.
- (iii) Let $U \in \tau^{S_2*}$, then $c_{\tau^{S_2}}(I_X - U) = (I_X - U)$ So, $c_{\tau^{S_1}}(I_X - U) \leq c_{\tau^{S_2}}(I_X - U) = (I_X - U)$, which gives $c_{\tau^{S_1}}(I_X - U) \leq (I_X - U)$ but $(I_X - U) \leq c_{\tau^{S_1}}(I_X - U) \Rightarrow c_{\tau^{S_1}}(I_X - U) = (I_X - U) \Rightarrow U \in \tau^{S_1*}$

4. FUZZY TOPOLOGY SUITABLE FOR FUZZY STACK

In this section, fuzzy stack satisfying a certain condition are considered. We applied some suitable condition on fuzzy stack S which makes collection τ^S suitable and compatible. Under this suitability condition, imposed on concerned stack, the collection τ^S will become $\{V - \beta: V \in \tau, B \notin S\}$.

Definition 4.1 - Let S be a fuzzy stack on fuzzy topological space (I^X, τ) . Then the fuzzy topology τ is suitable for fuzzy stack S , if corresponding to each $x_\alpha \leq A$, there exist $U \in Q(x_p)$ such that $A * U \notin S$, then $A \notin S$, for $A \in I^X$.

Definition 4.2 - For every fuzzy set A in X , we define fuzzy set \tilde{A} by $\tilde{A} = \{x_\alpha \leq A / x_\alpha \notin \psi_S(A)\}$.

Remark 4.2.1 - $\tilde{A} \wedge \psi_S(A) = 0_X$, for $A \in I^X$.

Remark 4.2.2 - $\tilde{A} \wedge \psi_S(\tilde{A}) = 0_X$, for $A \in I^X$.

Proposition 4.3 - For any fuzzy set $A, A = \tilde{A} \vee (A \wedge \psi_S(A))$.

Proposition 4.4 - Let S be a fuzzy stack on fuzzy topological

(I^X, τ) . Then τ is suitable for fuzzy stack S iff $A \wedge \phi_S(A) = 0_X$, implies $\phi_S(A) = 0_X$.

Proof - Since τ is suitable for fuzzy stack S . Let $A \wedge \phi_S(A) = 0_X$, so for each $x_\alpha \leq A$, we have $x_\alpha \not\leq \phi_S(A)$. Hence there exist $U \in Q(x_\alpha)$ such that $A * U \notin S$. Since τ is suitable for S , $A \notin S \Rightarrow \phi_S(A) = 0_X$. Conversely if $A \wedge \phi_S(A) = 0_X \Rightarrow A \notin S$. So τ is suitable for S . This completes the proof.

Proposition 4.5 - If $A \wedge \phi_S(A) = 0_X$, then $\phi_S(\tilde{A}) = 0_X$.

Remark 4.5.1 - If τ is suitable for S , then $\phi_S(\tilde{A}) = 0_X$.

Proposition 4.6 - For $A \in I^X$, if $\phi_S(A \wedge \phi_S(A)) = \phi_S(A)$, Then if $A \wedge \phi_S(A) = 0_X \Rightarrow \phi_S(A) = 0_X$.

Proof - Let $A \wedge \phi_S(A) = 0_X$. By given $\phi_S(A) = \phi_S(A \wedge \phi_S(A)) = \phi_S(0_X)$.

Proposition 4.7 - For every set A in X , if A contains no non empty set B with $B \leq \phi_S(B) \Rightarrow A \notin S$. Then $\tilde{A} \notin S$ for $A \in I^X$.

Proof - For $A \in I^X$, $\tilde{A} = \{x_\alpha \leq A : x_\alpha \not\leq \phi_S(A)\}$. We claim that \tilde{A} does not contain any non empty fuzzy set B s.t. $B \leq \phi_S(B)$. Then, $\tilde{A} \notin S$, if possible, let B be non empty fuzzy set contained in \tilde{A} such that $B \leq \phi_S(B)$. Let $x_\alpha \leq B$, then $x_\alpha \leq \tilde{A}$. But $B \leq \tilde{A}$ and so $x_\alpha \leq \phi_S(B) \leq \phi_S(\tilde{A})$. Also, $x_\alpha \leq \phi_S(B) \leq \phi_S(\tilde{A})$. Hence $x_\alpha \leq \tilde{A} \wedge \phi_S(\tilde{A})$, but $\tilde{A} \wedge \phi_S(\tilde{A}) = 0_X$, a contradiction.

Theorem 4.8 - Let (I^X, τ) be a fuzzy topological space and S be a fuzzy stack on I^X such that τ is suitable of S , then τ^S -closed fuzzy set can be expressed as a join of fuzzy set which is closed in (I^X, τ) and a fuzzy set which is not in fuzzy stack S .

Proof - Suppose A is a τ^S -closed set, then $A = A \vee \phi_S(A)$, this implies $\phi_S(A) \leq A$. Using proposition 4.3, $A = \tilde{A} \vee \phi_S(A)$, but $\tilde{A} \notin S$.

Theorem 4.9 - Let (I^X, τ) be a fuzzy topological space and S be a fuzzy stack on I^X such that τ is suitable for S . Let $\sigma = \{0_X, I_X\}$ denote fuzzy indiscrete topology on I^X , then $\tau^S = \sigma^S \cup \tau$.

Proof - Since $\sigma = \{0_X, I_X\}$ is fuzzy indiscrete topology on I^X . So I_X is only σ -qnb of every fuzzy point x_α in X . Then for $A \in I^X$, $x_\alpha \leq \phi_S(A) \Leftrightarrow A * I_X \in S \Leftrightarrow A \in S$. Thus for every $A \in S$, $\phi_S(A) = I_X$ and for every fuzzy set $A \notin S$, $\phi_S(A) = 0_X$. This implies $\psi_S(A) = A$ if $A \notin S$. $\sigma^S = \{U : I_X - U \notin S\}$, clearly $\sigma^S \subseteq \tau^S$ since for $V \in \tau^S$. Since $\tau \subseteq \tau^S$, $\sigma^S \subseteq \tau^S \Rightarrow \tau \cup \sigma^S \subseteq \tau^S$. Conversely, let $U \in \tau^S$, so $I - U = F \vee B$ where F is τ -closed and $B \notin S$ (using theorem 4.8). This gives, $U = (I_X - F) \wedge (I_X - B)$ where $I_X - F$ is τ -open and $I_X - B$ is σ^S -open so $U \in \tau \cup \sigma^S$.

Theorem 4.10 - Let S be fuzzy stack on (I^X, τ) with τ is suitable for S then $\tau^S = \{V - B : V \in \tau, B \notin S\}$.

Proof Let A be τ^S -closed fuzzy set then $\tau^S - cl(A) = A = A \vee \phi_S(A) \Rightarrow \phi_S(A) \leq A$. Since $A = \tilde{A} \vee (A \wedge \phi_S(A))$, we have $A = \tilde{A} \vee (A \wedge \phi_S(A))$. Using definition of \tilde{A} , $\phi_S(A) \wedge \tilde{A} = 0_X$. Since τ is suitable for $S \Rightarrow \tilde{A} \notin S$. $A = \tilde{A} \vee \phi_S(A)$ where $\phi_S(A)$ is τ -closed and $\tilde{A} \notin S$. We can write $A = \phi_S(A) + \tilde{A}$. $I_X - A = I_X - [\phi_S(A) + \tilde{A}] = \{[I_X - \phi_S(A)] - \tilde{A}\}$, here $I_X - \phi_S(A) \in \tau$ and $\tilde{A} \notin S$.

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